

Life-long learning program
ERASMUS ACCOMPANYING MEASURES
177090-LLP-1-2010-1-ES-ERASMUS-EAM

OIKODOMOS

Consolidation and expansion of a Virtual Campus

WORKPACKAGE 7 QUALITY ASSURANCE

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12/12/2011

Education and Culture DG

Lifelong Learning Programme

This project has been funded with support from the European Commission. This publication reflects the views only of the author, and the Commission cannot be held responsible for any use which may be made of the information contained therein.

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1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report summaries assorted data which has been collated during the project and systematically reviews the outputs produced against those proposed. The evaluation is designed to answer the question "how close did OIKODOMOS come to achieving its goals?"

2. INTRODUCTION

OIKODOMOS Virtual Campus was established with the aim of developing a structured virtual campus to support innovative pedagogic approaches that integrate on-line activities with the curricula at each partner institution. Alongside developing the platform the project explored the development of a blended learning model which supports learning and teaching interactions in both face-to-face and distance modes of teaching. This project set out to expand and consolidate the model created and tested the previous project, and to widen the scope and reach of our work. This report evaluates how successful we have been.

3. SCOPE OF THE EVALUATION

The initial plans for evaluation of this consolidation and dissemination project were based around achievement of the intended outcomes. The outputs and deviations from the project plan for each workpackage are reported within each of their reports. Here we briefly discuss the outputs for each workpackage, expanding on those which have not been discussed elsewhere. This report concludes with a discussion of the overall effectiveness of the project.

The core teaching partners were already familiar with use of the environments and the pedagogic process. Associate partners who joined the project provided new voices which gave further insight into the application of the pedagogic method and the use of the environments.

4. EVALUATION BY WORKPACKAGES

Within this section each work package and associated outputs are listed in numerical sequence. For each output the information and data sets which have been drawn on are described or listed. The discussion for each workpackage is concluded with a brief summary of the findings
Do we need some introduction here?

4.1 WP 2. Consolidation of the ICT platform

The table below summarizes the outputs foreseen for WP2 in the work program. The discussion which follows brings together the information from the different datasets.

Output no.	Output	Comments
3	Web portal consolidation	The new partnership discussed the design of the web-portal and it has been redesigned to enhance usability and access to the project tools and resources. The portal supplies direct entry links to all the tools and resources, including new resources such as the blogs and audiovisual presentations.
4	Workspaces consolidation	Following the review at the end of OIKODOMOS 1 and subsequent feedback the environments have been generally enhanced and the following new features added: on-line tutorial Online Glossary (e.g. OIKOpedia). Group submission option Task and their relationships visualisation and description editing tool
5	Case repository consolidation	Creating a communication space where the most relevant outputs of the repository can be effectively communicated to different user profiles. Creating specific learning modules where external users could interact with the content of the repository.
6	Communication spaces	Blogs communication spaces with external users,

4.1.1 Use of the Workspaces and Case Study Repository Environments

Results from the Joint Workshop evaluation questionnaire: (see Appendix 1 and 4.2.2 (WP 3 discussion))

OIKODOMOS Workspaces was used during the second semester of 2010-2011, as a learning environment to carry out the learning activities around the theme Proximity, which included the joint workshop in Istanbul. Below is an extract from the evaluation questionnaire conducted at the end of the workshop.

Q. No	Question	Mode	Median	No. of responses with this mode value
16	Please estimate your overall use of the tools below			
	Workspaces	2	2	38
	Case Study Repository	2	2	39
	Scaled: 1 – Very high to 4 - Very low			
	Workspaces	4		3
	Case Study Repository	4		6
<i>Total number of responses</i>				42
There were no responses in the open comments box				

The mode values of 2 indicates the use of both environments was high, which is what you would hope if the environments had been well integrated within the joint workshop activities. The small number of students scoring 4 indicates that the activities were successful in engaging the majority students in using the environments.

The main task (19, LA 25, see 4.2.2) following the workshop was for students to revisit and critically review their work during their time in Istanbul, producing a revised summary. Following completion of the task, the same group of students were asked the same question using an online questionnaire run post workshop. The results are given below.

Results from the post Joint Workshop (online) evaluation questionnaire (mid June 2011): (Appendix 4)

Q. No	Question	Mode	Median	No. of responses
23	Please estimate your overall use of the tools below			
	Workspaces	2	2	10
	Case Study Repository	4	4	10
	Scaled: 1 – Very high to 4 - Very low			
<i>Total number of responses</i>				10
No relevant responses in the general open comments boxes				

The mode value of 2 indicates that Workspaces use continued to be high following the joint workshop which reflects the students work on their task outputs.

The use of the Case Study Repository (CSR) was high prior and during the joint workshop, when students were exploring proximity and associated concepts. The mode value of 4 following the workshop indicates their use of the CSR decreased as the students continued to develop their ideas evolved during the workshop. These results suggest their efforts focussed on refining the work held in the Workspaces. In the post-workshop questionnaire only one student indicated their use of the CSR was very high.

4.1.2 Usability of the OIKODOMOS Work Spaces

4.1.2a Introduction

This section presents the method and results of the usability testing conducted for the Workspaces environment.

Usability is defined as “the effectiveness, efficiency and satisfaction with which specified users can achieve specified goals in particular environments” (ISO 9241-11). In other words, usability is the property of a mediated learning environment to support the users as transparently as possible towards the accomplishment of their learning goals.

The main goal of a usability evaluation is to detect the significant problems, obstacles and breakdowns for the user when interacting with a web application. For e-learning environments and applications, usability is a necessary (although not sufficient) condition for effective online learning. Easily locating and accessing the needed content, orienting oneself in the maze of different paths and nested pages of a structured website, avoiding being overloaded by the information clustered in a page, and being able to use the navigation architecture effectively are just some examples of important conditions for a learner to accomplish their learning tasks.

Hypermedia content offers access to vast information resources but they are frequently poorly structured (Acosta et al. 2003). If we assume that the organization and the usability of information is partly responsible for the quality of learning (Najjar, 1996), then a usable e-learning website is not just a resource with a nice “look & feel”, but a web application which communicates contents and structures interactions to facilitate the learning experience. However, it is clear that usability evaluation is just one aspect of the quality assessment of an e-learning environment. A highly usable online course does not guarantee demonstration of high quality in achievement of the learning outcomes. Nevertheless, shaping usability represents an important condition for the success of e-learning projects.

4.1.2b Method

The usability study was developed following the MiLE methodology (Triacca et al., 2004), in its e-learning adapted version. This method has already been used extensively and successfully for a variety of web application domains (e.g. educational institutions, cultural-heritage, public education, and e-government) (Matera et al., 2002; Bolchini et. al., 2003; Triacca et.al., 2003), and further tailored for use with e-learning web applications.

The goal of the study is to provide course developers and instructional designers with a structured “kit” of guidelines and practical suggestions for a cost-effective usability evaluation of their online application.

Luca Botturi and Marco Faré of the NewMinE Lab in Lugano developed the usability framework, consisting of user profiles, usability variables and scenarios with tasks. The usability framework, developed in December 2007, is presented in the OIKODOMOS Virtual Campus report, PR EP1.

The NewMinE lab prepared the form for collecting usability results, which was provided to URL, along with an example of a completed form.

4.1.3 Summary

The total sample was composed by 11 users, 5 students and 6 teachers. Two scenarios have been developed for a total of 22 tasks (10 for the students, 12 for the teachers (see picture below).

SCENARIO TEACHER – Creation of a new learning activity with related tasks

Task 01: Log in (with given login and password)
 Task 02: Create a new activity (Title: "Test2" and Description: "Test2")
 Task 03: Edit the description of the created activity: write "Test20" instead of "Test2"
 Task 04: Look for the Keywords of the activity LA25
 Task 05: Insert 3 keywords for the created activity: "Urban Analysis", "Learning Process" and "Mapping"
 Task 06: Add a learning outcome with the following description: "The student will be able to understand Test2"
 Task 07: Add the created learning outcome to your learning activity
 Task 08: Add your learning activity to an active workspace
 Task 09: Create two tasks for your learning activity: a new one called "Task001" and an existing one picked up from the task list
 Task 10: Create a group of two students (chiaraTest1 and chiaraTest2)
 Task 11: Assign the previous students to the tasks of your learning activity
 Task 12: Log out

SCENARIO STUDENT 01 -

Task 01: Log in (with given login and password)
 Task 02: Change password (change to the new given password)
 Task 03: Read the description of the task TK5
 Task 04: Find the learning resources associated to the task TK1
 Task 05: Submit a deliverable in TK21 task 1
 Task 06: Comment the work from the student "Workshop_Group10", Deliverable 3.jpg in task TK16
 Task 07: Identify the group where you are member and see the other members of the group
 Task 08: Identify a work done by another student of the same group
 Task 09: Read the evaluations given by teachers to the work XXX in task XXX
 Task 10: Log out

Student and teachers were asked to provide for each task described above the time to complete and the satisfaction (from 1 to 5, where 5 is the highest satisfaction).

In the following pages, the outcome of the student analysis will be presented first; second, the outcome of the teacher testing will be provided; finally, an annex with the full list of comments made by the users.

Student's outcome

- Every user completed all tasks
- High satisfaction, with the exception of task 5 (*Task 05. Submit a deliverable in TK21 task 1*): unfortunately only one student out of 5 made a comment about this task, stating that *the verification of successful delivery is missing*. The following table and chart shows the students' satisfaction for every task

	Task 1	Task 2	Task 3	Task 4	Task 5	Task 6	Task 7	Task 8	Task 9	Task 10
Student 1	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
Student 2	3	5	5	3	2	3	4	4	5	5
Student 3	5	5	5	5	3	4	5	5	4	5
Student 4	5	5	5	4	2	5	4	5	5	5
Student 5	5	5	5	4	3	5	4	5	5	5
AVERAGE	4,60	5,00	5,00	4,20	3,00	4,40	4,40	4,80	4,80	5,00

- Very high difference in time to complete the tasks: we perceive that this won't be a data to take into consideration: e.g. according to the figures, a user stated that it took 30 minutes to log in, but then there was the maximum satisfaction (value = 5)
- Other meaningful comments were a browser graphic problem in task 2 (where to create a new activity) and the login position in the first page.

Teachers' outcome

- Some tasks were not completed (or not fully completed) by some teachers: task 9 for teacher 3 (*Task 09: Create two tasks for your learning activity: a new one called "Task001" and an existing one picked up from the task list*); task 11 for teacher 5 (*Task 11: Assign the previous students to the tasks of your learning activity*). Teacher 6 didn't compile the form for the last three tasks, so there's no chance to know whether they were completed or not.
- Lower satisfaction compared to the students: some of the tasks were well below the value = 3 (average satisfaction): task 3 (*Task 03: Edit the description of the created activity: write "Test20" instead of "Test2"*), task 7 (*Task 07: Add the created learning outcome to your learning activity*) and task 9 (already mentioned). The following table and chart shows the teachers' satisfaction for every task

	Task 1	Task 2	Task 3	Task 4	Task 5	Task 6	Task 7	Task 8	Task 9	Task 10	Task 11 (T)	Task 12 (T)
Teacher 1	4	2	2	4	2	4	2	4	3	4	4	5
Teacher 2	3	3	4	4	2	2	2	3	3	2	4	5
Teacher 3	5	5	3	3	5	4	5	5	3	5	5	5
Teacher 4	5	4	3	5	5	5	3	4	3	4	4	5
Teacher 5	/	4	2	4	3	3	3	3	2	4	1	5
Teacher 6	5	3	3	3	3	3	2	3	3	/	/	/
AVERAGE	4,40	3,50	2,83	3,83	3,33	3,50	2,83	3,67	2,83	3,80	3,60	5,00

- Teachers made much more comments than the students: EVERY teacher complained about where to find the tasks (i.e. the difference between the login spaces) for task 9. The problem of the difference between admin login and workspace login also comes up in task 2, for a couple of teachers. This could be the most important issue that these user tests have found. The majority of teachers found that it was hard to find how to edit the description of the activity (task 3).

4.1.4 Case Study Repository

As indicated above (4.1.1) the workshop evaluation questionnaire revealed that use of the CSR prior and during the workshop was high, but low following the workshop. There were no comments reflecting the usability of the environment, so students from a new partners, Cottbus, were asked to provide feedback on the CSR, using the questionnaire given in Appendix 2. Only 3 responses were received and these indicated that there were no consistent problems in the use of the environment. Some comments indicated aspects of usability that merit further investigation such as uploading pictures. Responses which relate to the overall experience are given below:

Q. No 32	How do you evaluate your overall experience in using the OIKODMOS Case Repository?
	Nice page, but i hope that many other universities will upload many other case studies
	It was great to have a look at other works not only from the same university
	Not everything works the way it should, but it's still in progress and I like the essential idea of the project

4.1.5 Communication Spaces

The OIKODOMOS project portal provides links to the Workspaces, Case Study Repository, support resources and dissemination media, namely project and partner blogs. The blogs were established to provide more open communication channels with external users (e.g. those who are not registered and therefore do not have access into the digital platform –Workspaces, Case study repository, OIKOpedia). The variations in traffic are discussed in 4.1.5.b below.

For the joint workshop activities students were contacted by email lists. The Workspaces environment includes a blog and an event log through which information and updates are provided, alongside the instructions for each learning activity and task. Students also used their own channels for communication during collaborative activities, which included direct email, Facebook and Skype.

4.1.5.a OIKOpedia

This is a wiki based system which allows partners to add definitions and/or descriptions of terminology used within OIKODOMOS, primarily to support new users of the system. It is at an early stage of development but expected to grow over the next few years.

4.1.5.b Results from Blogs, Workspace and Case Repository visit analysis, November 2010 – October 2011

A number of blogs were established to enhance communication between the OIKODOMOS partnership and the wider community. Access information was collated via Google Analytics and as summary of the results is given below. The full data sets and more detailed breakdown of the results is given in Appendix 5.

OIKODOMOS blog (<http://project-oikodomos.blogspot.com/>):

The blog has been used a lot during the year, with more than 3634 pages visited in the period November 2010-October 2011. The greatest use occurred in parallel with the International Joint Workshop organized in Istanbul in May, and during the month of October 2011, before the final conference.

The day with the most pages visited was October 5th 2011 (139 pages visited).

Belgium and Spain where, in the overall period, the countries which accessed the blogs most. The most viewed post was about the joint (international) workshop on Housing and Proximity with 254 views.

Partners' blogs: (<http://project-oikodomos.blogspot.com/>; <http://lasalle-oikodomos.blogspot.com/>; <http://fastu-oikodomos.blogspot.com/>; <http://sintlucas-oikodomos.blogspot.com/>; <http://iug-oikodomos.blogspot.com/>; <http://emu-oikodomos.blogspot.com/>):

The most used blog was that of La Salle. It was very rich in posts (73 posts) and the visits were quite distributed during the overall period, with a total of 3,069 pages visited over the project year with peaks during the last month of 2010, the first months of 2011, and before the final conference. Most of the visits to the Spanish blog came from Spain (1.629 page views by Spain). This can be explained by the Spanish partner dissemination and by the quality of the contents of the posts.

Another blog well used was that of Sint-Lucas. It had 18 posts rich in content and in the overall period counted 1169 page visited (especially from Belgium) with a peak in June 2011.

The others partners blogs were used a little less for communication in comparison to the blogs of the Spanish and the Belgium partners. They generally had less posts and less visits. FASTU's blog had 412 pages views, IUG's blog 309 page views, EMU's blog 322 page views.

The OIKODOMOS webportal (www.oikodomos.org):

The OIKODOMOS portal had a consistent number of page visits throughout the overall period, modulated by expected seasonal variation (less access during the summer break).

The overall page views were 8.030 with the number of visits of 2901. The average time on site is 3 minutes and 7 seconds, which is a sign that people visiting the website take time to read the contents.

A very interesting aspect was the number of visits from the countries of new associate partners, especially Germany, demonstrating the positive response to dissemination within the new institutions. The map below shows the distribution of countries accessing the portal .

This results show that the web site has been visited by people from 75 countries, the greatest density of visits being identified by the darkest green (colour). The first 25 countries listed included visits numbering >10. However, the number of visits doesn't reflect the real level of interest, for example one country had 4 visits but with an average 'time on site' of 18 minutes.

OIKODOMOS Workspaces and Case study repository (www.oikodomos.org/workspaces and <http://www.oikodomos.org/caserepository/>):

The Workspaces environment counted 6.126 visits during the project year, with 1.340 unique visitors. The case repository platform counted 2.284 visits during the project year, with 606 unique visitors.

Both OIKODOMOS Workspaces and Case study repository have been used by interested users, staying a long time on the websites (nearly 11 minutes average for Workspaces, more than 12 minutes average for the CSR) and visiting many pages (more than 12 pages/visit for Workspaces and more than 10 pages/visit for the CSR).

The Workspaces has been used more in the period before and during the workshop in Istanbul, while the CSR has also been used a lot during the months of June and July 2011. For the CSR there has been a marked increase (+80,66%) in the number of visitors between the first 6 months (November 2010-April 2011) of the project with respect to the second period (May – October 2011). This is mostly due to the use of the repository in a course carried out by BTU Cottbus. This is why Germany accounted for 875 visits in the second period of the project (May – October 2011), the highest number per country.

Summary

The results above indicate that the web portal has become an effective medium for providing information about OIKODOMOS and facilitates access to the various project resources and environments. The Workspaces and Case Study Repository have been refined, and the evaluations indicate that they are generally useful environments which are drawing increasing numbers of users. Blogs have been made available to all partners to enhance communication beyond the partnership. Where the partners have actively used the blogs there has been significant use by the local and wider communities.

4.2 WP3. Consolidating and expanding the pedagogic model

The discussion below primarily brings together information about the learning and teaching activities and their evaluation in an evaluation of these aspects of the project.

4.2.1 Output summary

The two outputs are described in the table below:

Output no.	Output	Comments
1	Compendium	This OIKODOMOS Compendium provides an overview of the OIKODOMOS project and how to use the project outputs. It contains a summary of the underlying theory and methodologies employed, examples of use, reflections from teachers who have used the virtual campus for teaching, and individuals and information on access to the virtual campus and support resources. The compendium is intended to support new users in setting up and using the virtual campus for their own activities.
3	International Workshop	The International (Joint) Workshop brought together students from the partner and other institutions, initially working at a distance on tasks within project teams formed to prepare for the workshop. The virtual teams experienced working face-to-face when they came together for the workshop, and continued their work through tasks following the workshop.

4.2.2 Consolidation of the pedagogic model

The pedagogic model was developed in conjunction with the workshops from the previous project, and has been described in Madrazo and Ridy (2011). It involves a complex blend of learning activities within and between institutions, groups formed from students in different institutions who work virtually and face-to-face. A Joint Workshop provides a common focus around which learning activities and tasks can be designed, climaxing in the face-to-face Joint Workshop where the students meet their working group colleagues for the first time. This interweaving of tasks is illustrated below. Task 19 was the final task in the series listed below, which were built around the Joint Workshop in Istanbul.

- LA22 TK4 Mapping Proximity: LINDEN
- LA21 TK5 What is proximity?
- LA22 TK7 Mapping the proximity - Bratislava suburbs
- LA25 TK16 Proximity: extracting themes.
- LA22 TK17 In Situ Göksu Quarter: Signs of Proximity.
- LA22 TK18 Mapping Proximity: Göksu Quarter
- **LA25 TK19 Göksu Quarter Revisited**

The Learning Activities (LA) titles were:

- LA21 Defining Proximity
- LA22 Exploring Proximities: Housing & Urban Context
- LA25 Discussing Proximities

Task 19 description is replicated below, and illustrates the description of a task based on the work done previously during the workshop.

Task 19, Göksu Quarter Revisited

The outcomes of task 18 (In Situ **Göksu Quarter**) were most interesting and proved a critical and coherent attitude related to the site and its potentials. However, the short available time for presentation and its the format did not always allow to frame the urban proposals. The following questions, aiming at a broader reflection about proximity, remain:

How can we relate the proposals at different levels to the concept of proximity, what is the (social) model behind the proposed interventions?

Can we define the proposal as a unique strategy or were reference projects used? If yes, how were they used?

How can we relate the proposals to a broader discourse on low or high dense landscapes and its possible (re)densification? Did we base our interventions on tactics of densification or did we only reconfigure the existing urban fabric and do we know why?

When did we use systematic approaches? When a structural approach? (see feedback and evaluations)

What is the vision behind the proposal and which strategies can be used to implement them?

This task of Revisiting the proposed Urban Projects provides some distance of the work done and will try to frame the proposals. A coherent and critical description of the proposal is to be elaborated by each mixed group with the following objective:

-frame the proposed intervention conceptually (see remaining questions above)

-describe the proposal in a way external students or teachers could understand the proposal

Outputs / Deadline

4.2.2.a Evaluation of the Workshop

The evaluation employed a student focussed questionnaire (Fill, 2005). The questionnaire was a development of that used during the three workshops implemented in the previous OIKODOMOS project. It was distributed to 45 students at the end of the final session, 42 responses were received. The full set of questions is given in Appendix 1.

The spread of questions was primarily designed to look at students learning and teaching experiences pre and during the workshop, but included a few questions on students use of the environments (based on the work of Riddy and Fill, (2004)), and on their response to the overall experience. A summary of the questionnaire scores is given below in Table 1 below along with the sections in which they were organised.

Table 1: Istanbul Joint Workshop Evaluation Questionnaire results

Data scaled:

1-4, Strongly agree, Agree, Disagree, Strongly disagree, + Don't know & Not Applicable as N/A.

Q.No	Questions	Mode	Median	Total no. of commen
Pre Joint Workshop evaluation questions				
11	Before going to the Joint Workshop I was clear about the purpose of the international cooperation in our (school) learning activities	2	2	1
12	The Learning Activities created by teachers in the Workspace were relevant, appropriate and clear.	2	2	6
13	From the start of these activities I was given full descriptions of the learning activity, including learning objectives/outcomes	2	2	1
14	The learning activities in my school before going to the Joint Workshop were well integrated with the learning activities during the Joint Workshop	2	2	3

15	I used this Workshop Workspace regularly before the workshop to gain the information about the site.	2	2	3
16	Tools used (see appendix)			N/A
17	Using these tools I was able to access enough information to prepare for the work in Bratislava	2	2	0
18	Electronic/computer communication helped me to get to know the participants from the other schools well enough to help collaboration before going to the Joint Workshop	2	2	6
19	The academic support at my University was sufficient for preparation of the learning activities to be carried out in the Joint Workshop	2	2	2
20	The processes to get technical and academic support were adequate	2	2	1
21	The response times to questions from learners by staff were adequate	2	2	2
22	I discussed information on the Joint Workshop site with other students and teachers in advance of the workshop	2	2	6
23	I found students contributions to the discussions helpful	2	2	3
24	I found professors contributions to the discussions helpful	1	2	5
25	Working online collaboratively with students from other countries has been a good experience	1	1	7
	Joint Workshop Evaluation			
26	I was clear about the purpose/objective of the Joint Workshop when I arrived	2	2	2
27	The Introduction / briefing sessions made clear all aspects of the Joint Workshops	2	2	2
28	I was clear about the competences or learning outcomes to be gained from completing the workshop before arriving	2	2	0
29	I am clear about the way in which my work during the workshop will be assessed	2	2	3
30	The taught sessions were relevant and appropriate	2	2	5
31	The taught sessions were clearly presented	2	2	3
32	I thought the taught sessions were well integrated with the workshop theme	2	2	1
33	I thought the taught sessions fitted well with the work in groups	2	2	1
34	There was adequate access to computing resources	2	2	8
35	I had enough time to do the work	2	2.5	2
36	I had enough time not working / free time	4	4	5
37	I understand what work I have to do in my institution which follows on from this joint workshop	2	2	2
38	I was able to communicate effectively with the members of my group	2	2	5
39	What was you most important or interesting learning?	N/A	N/A	51
40	What did you like, what is done well?	N/A	N/A	46
41	What could be done differently?	N/A	N/A	54
42	Any other comments?	N/A	N/A	18
	Total no. of comments			254

Summary of Table 1 results

All questions except two have mode and median values which are the same, indicating limited spread of the scores. The majority of scores are the same and equal 2, with three values differing, discussed further below. This contrasts strongly with the post Bratislava workshop questionnaire (previous project), in which 75% of questions were scored 1, the remainder 2. The former questionnaire was web based, delivered electronically post workshop, and the students were from a smaller group of institutions who had participated in the project for 2 years.

The number of students comments associated with each of the questions are also listed. Apart from where large numbers are recorded, the majority of the comments refer to comments on single points, indicating a diversity of opinion from which statistically meaningful conclusions cannot be drawn.

Comments from the open questions included:

Table 2: Comments to selected questions

Question No (no of comments)	Comments summary
38 (5) I was able to communicate effectively with the members of my group	100% were negative about the ability to communicate in their group, either because of their own level of English or because of the level of others.
40 (46) What did you like, what is done well?	9% found the tasks were good 22% teaching and interactions helpful 20% found the group interaction useful 13% commented on good organisation 9% appreciated the working methods
41 (54) What could be done differently?	6% were –ve about the role of the lectures 19% commented on timing issues, wanting more time for the workshop/tasks, to see the city, to interact with other groups 7% had some difficulty working with the organisation, or working within their group
42 (18) Any other comments?	50% commented on the workshop being a good experience

4.2.2.b Summary of Consolidation

All questions relate to evaluation of the overall approach, but the questions in Table 1 with numbers in **bold** relate more directly to the effectiveness of the learning and teaching process. All these questions had mode values of 2, collectively indicating that the students had found the overall pedagogical process effective. The same basic pedagogic model was used in the original OIKODOMOS project and these results indicate the experience from conducting learning activities were successfully brought into this project.

However, this joint workshop cohort of students were selected from a larger number of institutions and were more diverse, so it's difficult to draw any meaningful conclusion from comparisons between the results from the last joint OIKODOMOS workshop in Bratislava and the results from this workshop in Istanbul. The lack of negative comments on the learning and teaching process indicates that there are no major issues, and there were a greater percentage of comments on the success of the groups than expressing difficulties with the groups (questions 40 and 41 respectively). However, as the members of a group being able to work as an effective team is crucial to them completing their tasks, it's worth considering how the group dynamics can be monitored and enhanced. Appointment of a mentor for each group whose role is to provide general guidance on organisation and planning and to act as mediator for any difficulties arising from the dynamics of the group/individuals would be a way to alleviate such problems. Ability to speak English / a common language has also been highlighted as a difficulty, and needs to be better addressed in the participant selection process.

4.2.3 Associate partners and other institutions

As indicated earlier, BTU Cottbus carried out a course using the Case Repository, with the participation of 98 students from the first year of an architecture program.

Other associated partners which joined the project during this year and participated in the learning activities, in the following way:

- Gebze Institute of Technology, with a group of 5 students and 1 teacher in the International Workshop. Continued with the collaborative activity post workshop but not as part of their formal curriculum.

- School of Architecture of Valencia, with a group of 7 teachers who evaluated the work done by students from partner institutions

The total number of students participating in the Virtual Campus activities in the academic year 2010-2011 amounts to 344 from 8 participating institutions.

Including the above 11 new institutions from across Europe have engaged in the project activities during this year of which five have signed a formal agreement as associate partners.

4.2.4 New support resources

To make the pedagogic methodology and environments more accessible to new or potential users the following guidance and information materials were produced.

Learning design with OIKODOMOS Workspaces. An introduction to learning design with OIKODOMOS to support participating teachers

OIKODOMOS Workspaces in 5 Steps: an application case. An example of application of the OIKODOMOS pedagogic model to support participating teachers.

OIKODOMOS Pedagogy. Narrated powerpoint providing and introduction to the underlying pedagogic methodology.

Housing Learning Module. A module with learning content on housing suited to non-professional learners (Output 12 in WP4).

4.2.5 Staff Feedback

Due to the time constraints which partners found themselves under the original questionnaire was modified down to a shorter version (Appendix 3). Only one member of staff from an associate partner made themselves available for interview by Skype, and one other responded to the questions via email. The feedback indicated:

- Established partners were able to integrate the learning activities with their institutional programs, but it was more difficult for associate partners who joined the project shortly before the joint workshop.
- The student outputs from the joint workshop were of good to very good quality
- It was difficult for some schools to integrate post workshop activities with their programs because of entering an exam period and the short time left before their term finished,

4.2.6 Conclusion

This section has looked at the consolidation and expansion of the pedagogic model. The pedagogic model has proved robust and has been successfully introduced and used by new partners within a collaborative joint international workshop. The joint workshop added new resources and a further example of the pedagogic process to the Workspaces environment. Support for application of the pedagogic model has been enhanced through addition of the Compendium and new support resources.

The degree of educational integration which can be achieved is effected by the positioning of the joint workshop during the academic year and the lead-in time available for integration with OIKODOMOS learning activities

4.3 WP4. Expanding learning activities to non-academic environments

Below is a summary of the main activities and products which have been introduced to foster greater engagement by wider communities.

Output no.	Output	Summary of Events
1	Exhibition Bratislava	15.02. – 01.03.2011, Exhibition, total attendance ~100, age range from 20- over 70. Led by teachers from FASTU with over 50% of the attendees being from the community, 25% students and the others a mixture of professionals and council representatives. Posters displayed and used as a stimulus for discussions
		04.03. – 18.03.2011, Exhibition, total attendance ~160, age range from 20- over 70. Led by teachers from FASTU with over 60% of the attendees being from the community, 30% students, the others a mixture of professionals and council representatives. Posters displayed and used as a stimulus for discussions
		04.03. – 18.03.2011, Exhibition, total attendance ~110, age range from 20- over 70. Led by teachers from FASTU with over 65% of the attendees being from the community, 22% students, the others a mixture of professionals and council representatives. Posters displayed and used as a stimulus for discussions
10	Exhibition Grenoble	June-July 2011. Se former à l'Urbanisme - Episode d'Architecture". Opened with a mixed group of 40 participants including students, architects, planners and citizens (~30), but was open to the citizens of Grenoble for the remaining time.
		June 2011?. Café de l'Architecture, debates with residents of the new housing eco-district, 50 citizens, 2 teachers, 3 architects. This event used the OIKODOMOS workshop outputs as resources.
11	Exhibition North Cyprus	25.10.2011, OIKODOMOS project exhibition, total attendance ~250, age range from 20- 60. Led by staff from EMU with over 70% of the attendees being students, the others members of the faculty, professionals and general public.
	Other (Barcelona)	06.05-07.05.2011 International Workshop. "Architecture, research and profession", total attendance ~70, most in age range from 30 – 60, 15 countries represented. Research conference in which an OIKODOMOS poster was presented as example of pedagogic research.
12	Housing Learning Module	<i>A module with learning content on housing suited to non-professional learners??... Building on the material from the workshops</i> IUG designed a Housing Learning module and proposition for testing by academic and non-academic learners in the OIKODOMOS Workspaces
13	Learning Communities	<i>Creating spaces of interaction on-line/on-site with non-academic learners.</i> Las Salle has created a learning community based around widening the community engaged in planning discussions associated with the neighbourhood Plus Ultra, Barcelona.
14	Participatory actions	<i>Local meeting.</i> <i>Aimed at the general public and local authorities, this will also be of interest to students and to teachers & professionals in the architecture and urban planning.</i>

Summary

Outputs 10 and 11 were closely related to 13 and 14. The exhibitions served the role of stimulating discussions between academics, members of the local council and the public. The blogs discussed under WP2, were a medium which could be used to encourage wider discussion, and were used to different effect by the partners involved.

4.4 WP5. Virtual and Physical conference

Below is a summary of the three main outputs associated with this workpackage. A *brief description* is given in *italics*, followed by an update it's evolution during the project. Each is discussed in more detail below.

Output no.	Output	Comments
15	Virtual spaces: next generation	<i>Virtual conference / online discussion fora.</i> This collection of online forums were linked with conference themes and intended to prime and supplement discussions which took place during the conference. Despite establishing discussions and wide dissemination of their availability there were very few contributions. This is further discussed below.
16	Virtual Spaces: Specification and Design	<i>Conference</i> The focus of the conference was shifted towards more of a housing focus and less of a virtual spaces focus, as originally planned. . This was decided because the teaching partners felt a housing focus would attract wider interest and that it could include an innovation in learning strand, in which there could be a discussion about the use of virtual spaces. The new conference theme was Innovating Housing Learning and it encompassed three themes: Innovating and Housing, Housing and Learning and Learning and Innovation . This change in the conference focus also needed to be reflected in the virtual discussions and the conference proceedings.
17	Virtual Spaces: Shaping the future selected papers	<i>Collection of papers based on the conference presentations</i> This publication was to be based on discussions taking place during the conference. With the change in focus of the conference the collection of papers reflects the new conference theme.

4.4.1 Virtual spaces: next generation

As preparation for the international conference in Brussels, a series of online discussions were established utilizing Vanilla Forums, linked to from the webportal. The individual forums were listed under their categories below:

Pedagogic Innovation

Assessment of Creative Work
OIKODOMOS Environments / Workspaces discussion

Contemporary Housing Design and Planning: New Challenges

Housing as Product
Restructuring Public/Private Space
Built Environment as Complex Information System
Housing Design without a brief

Conference 2011

Connecting Individuals and the Role of Architecture Education: Housing Design or Social Engineering
Pragmatic Design Studios

The forum was disseminated through:

- eCAADe, Education and Research in Computer Aided Architectural Design in Europe
150 members and a emailing list of 700
- EAEE European Association for Architectural Education
38 countries, 140 members representing 5000 faculty and 120,000 students
- Snt Lucas Facebook group

- Personal email list of OIKODOMOS partners
- Around 200 individuals, mainly academic architects and urban planners, but also some individuals working in commercial environments.

In addition the October OIKODOMOS conference was advertised to other mailing lists such as the Association of European Schools of Planning newsletter (AESOP, 28 June 2011).

The first two online discussion categories were activated around 4 weeks in advance of the conference, and reminders being sent out to the same lists around a week before. The latter category (Conference 2011) was established immediately after the conference (the next day) in response to around 50% of the conference audience agreeing to participate. A reminder was also sent to conference participants with the appropriate weblink. During the period of the project there was one further contribution to these forum, and since the 1st November there have been another three.

Summary

Theoretically there was an audience for these discussions, even if it was only the conference participants who we could be expected to be interested. It's well known that online discussions need a moderators input to initiate and stimulate further discussion and the OIKODOMOS facilitators played their part appropriately, but there was very limited opportunity to develop the discussions. Research into the application and stimulation of online discussions within the disciplines of architecture and pedagogy in architecture requires further investigation, but that is beyond the scope of this project.

4.4.2 OIKODOMOS Conference Evaluation: October 2011

Towards the end of the second (last) day of the conference participants were asked to complete a short evaluation questionnaire. The results are summarised and discussed below.

3.4.1.a) Methodology

The questionnaires used Likert scales with open response boxes. As the number of responses from each cohort was small analysis has been based on mapping and interpretation of the descriptive statistics, informed by the participant's comments.

The spread of questions was designed to look at the scope of the participants and their impression about the conference. A summary of the questionnaire scores is given below in Table 2 below after which there is further discussion of the associated open comments and separate open questions.

Demographic information:

17 questionnaires returned from 35 participants (registered, there were also un-registered local student participants)

11 countries, 12 institutions

10 University teachers

1 postgraduate

3 undergraduates

1 University collaborator,

1 elearning specialist

1 blank

Table 2: OIKODOMOS Conference, scored data question results**Data scaled:**

1-4, Strongly agree, Agree, Disagree, Strongly disagree, + Don't know / Not Applicable.

Questionnaire No.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	Mode	Median
Questions																			
1 It was easy to find information on this event	2	1	2	1	1	3		3	2	3	1	1	2	2	?	2	1	2	2
2 The event was well organised	1	1	1	1	1	1		1	1	1	2	1	2	2	1	2	1	1	1
3 I found the selection of presentations appropriate for the conference	2	1	2	2	1	2		1	1	2	2	3	2	3	2	2	2	2	2
4 I found the presentations informative	2	1	2	2	2	2		1	1	1	2	4	2	3	2	2	2	2	2
5 The conference has increased my knowledge about the OIKODOMOS project	1	3	1	2	1	1		2	5	1	1	3	1	2	3	5	2	1	1.5
6 The event provided opportunities for networking	1	1	2	1	1	1		2	1	2	1	3	2	2	2	2	1	1	1.5
7 I enjoyed the conference	1	1	2	1	1	1		1	1	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	1	1

Discussion

The scores indicate that there were some difficulties finding information on the event, that some of the presentations could have been more focused towards the conference activity and better presented. The conference was well organised, strong on disseminating information about OIKODOMOS and providing networking opportunities. The scores of 5 under question 5 came from individuals associated with the OIKODOMS project (and were not included in the statistical calculations). The scores above are further illuminated by the results of open questions presented below.

Table 3: OIKODOMOS Conference, comments associated with the scored and open feedback questions

Q.No	Mode	No of comments	
3	2	4	3 confirmed the scores, comments included that the presentations were interesting
4	2	4	3 found at least half the presentations interesting, 1 found the main message missing
5	1	2	All found info on the way the platform was being used interesting
6	1	2	All confirmed the mode score
7	1	1	confirmed the mode score
8	N/A	12	11 were positive about the networking and friendly nature of the conference 4 commented on the discussion opportunities around conference topics 1 on exploring the teaching of housing "in the studio"
9	M/A	9	1 wanted to see more of the local environment 3 larger involvement of students 2 wanted more help with accommodation 2 commented on the poor time management of the presentations 2 commented on the poor wireless connectivity within the conference spaces (where it's needed if you want a vibrant virtual aspect to the conference) 2 commented on the dispersion of presentations from conference issues
10	N/A	4	1 Better internet connection needed 1 wanted more engagement with the pedagogical aspects 1 wanted a better selection of papers 1 wanted the conference to be longer – for more discussion time

How did people hear about the event:

Question	No of responses	
How did you hear about the event?	17	10 from partners 4 by email 1 from a blog 1 from a colleague 1 from a teacher

Despite wide circulation of conference information through email lists, the OIKODOMOS web and Facebook sites, the most successful recruitment has been via direct contact with one or other of the partners. This figure may be higher than indicated because the origin of the 4 email notifications is not known.

WP5 Summary

The original design of the conference and associated activities and documents were changed, but both the conference and associated collection of papers were successfully completed. The topics of online forums were carefully selected and populated to link in with the conference activities but failed to gain the attention of the conference participants or a wider audience, despite wide dissemination. The lack of success of the latter would require further investigation before any satisfactory conclusions could be drawn.

4.5 WP6 Publications

The table below summarises the publications that were planned for the project and the actual papers produced.

Output no.	Output (Planned papers)	Papers delivered
18	Towards Virtual Architecture and Urban Planning: the findings of OIKODOMOS	Towards Virtual Architecture (Global Time Conference on Technology, Innovation, Mediation and Education, Feb 2011)
19	Virtual Spaces: Design Studios within a Virtual Campus Design	The Oikodomos Virtual Campus: a networked-based model of education (EdMedia, June 2011)
20	Oikodomos update	OIKODOMOS Virtual Campus: Constructing learning processes in collaboration (eCAADE, Sept 2011) [Towards Virtual Architecture (ECER Sept 2010)]

The planned publications have been completed and other related publications and activities have contributed to dissemination about OIKODOMS.

4.6 WP7 Quality assurance

The two main outputs are listed in the table and described in the sections below.

Output no.	Output	Comments
21	Evaluation Plan	The evaluation plan was devised early in the project and feedback sought from the project partners. The completed plan was disseminated to all partners by Feb 2011, providing a guide for the collection of data throughout the project.
22	Evaluation Report	This document

4.6.1 What has been the wider impact of OIKODOMOS?

4.6.1.a Involvement of other institutions

As indicated in 4.2.3 11 institutions have engaged in OIKODOMOS activities and 5 have become formerly connected through signing partner agreements. There is currently a new active Workspace (Housing Reagents) in which the lead partner and two associated partners are engaged with collaborative learning activities, leading to a Workshop in Barcelona from 14-16 December. During this year, we expect to have two more Workspaces which will be managed by new partners: ISCTE, from Lisbon, and ETS Valencia.

4.6.1.b Scope of dissemination

There has been wide exposure of OIKODOMOS using a variety of media and opportunities as indicated in 3.4.1 above and in the following workpackage reports: WP3 (Expanding learning activities to non-academic environments), WP5 (International Conference) and WP6 (Publications). The main conferences at which papers were presented are listed below. Although the first falls outside of the project period it was part of the continuum between the original OIKODOMOS project and this continuation year.

-ECER, Helsinki, 25-27.8.10 European Conference on Educational Research attracted 1750 researchers from 70 countries, across the spectrum of educational activities. The conference is organised into networks and this paper was listed under the Higher Education network offerings.

- AACE Global TIME, 22-24.2.11 Conference concerned with the use of ICT in Education. -Online Conference on Technology, Innovation, Media & Education attracted over 60 registered participants presenting papers from 17 countries, predominantly from academic institutions but also from the commercial world and professional bodies.

- ED MEDIA, Lisbon, Portugal. 26-29.6.11. EdMedia brought together 800 participants from 60 countries, teachers, researchers, software vendors, instructional designers, administrators and multimedia authors from a range of fields which included pedagogy, educational psychology, computational science and information science.

- ECAADE conference, Ljubljana, Slovenia, 21-24.9.11. The conference was attended by over 100 teachers, researchers and students from Europe as well from other countries around the world. During the forum discussion, OIKODOMOS was mentioned as a contribution to the current debate to the pedagogy of virtual design studios.

- OIKODOMOS International Conference, 27-28.10.11. Presentation of the project to the conference participants: 35 teachers, researchers and students.

The **Joint Workshop** in Istanbul included student and teacher participants who were not part of the partnership and the event utilised speakers from Istanbul who presented information and a local view of the development potential of the site being considered. The students produced summary documents of their work which were made available to other students back in their home institutions. These and posters outputs from previous OIKODOMOS workshops were used as resources for the dissemination events listed under 4.3 (WP4).

The **OIKODOMOS International Conference** was widely publicised by partner institutions who used their national networks of contacts to obtain a wider reach. Key note speakers from architecture and housing pedagogy provided insight into their work and it's relationship with the exploration of OIKODOMOS. Other presentations gave specific information about OIKODOMOS activities and /or encompassed housing and technology support learning in architecture and urban planning.

Lead Staff from all institutions have involved colleagues in OIKODOMOS activities. Involvement ranges from technical support through participation in project meetings to active participation in LAs and tasks. Partners have also raised OIKODOMOS at formal and informal meetings within and beyond their institutions, ranging from discussions with colleagues to wider dissemination events.

4.6.2 Summary

The scope of dissemination has been wide. All staff indicate that their work with OIKODOMOS has engaged them with deeper reflection on the educational process, with how they might develop their work and the wider educational processes within their institution. Alongside the immediately observable impacts of their activities within their immediate sphere of activity, there have been many more connections made with the local communities and other educators.

OIKODOMOS has improved the environments of the virtual campus and engaged a wider group of users in applying the pedagogic methodology via the virtual campus. The platform will continue to be made available to partners and other interested parties, and this is stimulating wider interest from educators and potential students. Partners have expressed their intention to continue to use the platform so there is likely to be wider impact as the use of these tools begins to penetrate the communities more deeply.

The results can be considered against the Rugby Team Impact Framework (2008) indicators. This framework was designed to evaluate the impact of "training and development of researchers in higher education", but it is instructive to apply the model in slightly modified form to OIKODOMOS.

The impact indicators are summarized below, with more details being available from the reference.

Domain of Effects		
Development of infrastructure		
Level 0	Foundation	Developed programmes, increased capacity
Partners participate in project based activity		
Level 1	Reaction	Participant reaction to activity
Level 2	Learning	Attitude change eg improved knowledge, increased skill level
Level 3	Behaviour	Behaviour change eg reflective self-aware, confident
Results		
Level 4	Outcomes	External impact, eg application of L&T methodology and use of the platform, improvement of student learning experience

The discussion above indicates that OIKODOMOS has continued to work effectively on levels 0-3, in particular the virtual campus and associated pedagogic methodology have proved to be robust and have become more deeply embedded within the partner institutions.

Factors which contribute to wider impact at level 4 include the take-up and use of the virtual campus and pedagogic methodology by new institutions, both as members of the partnership and as new collaborators who wish to be more involved. This level also considers the wider impact through dissemination activities. The conference presentations have potentially increased the exposure to people from 70-100 countries and in excess of over 2000 professionals, many of whom are academics and will further disseminate work of interest to their colleagues and students.

Partner's exhibitions and local events have disseminated the information about OIKODOMOS methodologies and outputs to their local communities, involving over 300 local people from the vicinities of Bratislava, Grenoble and North Cyprus, alongside professionals with a working interest in housing and urban planning disciplines.

Eleven new partners have participated in OIKODOMS activities of which 5 have signed formal partner agreements, a strong indicator of sustainable expansion of the partnership and of growing interest in what OIKODOMOS has produced.

5. CONCLUSION

The discussion above indicates that all the project outputs have been achieved but attempts to establish a virtual conference met with little success. The results from joint workshop student questionnaire indicate that OIKODOMOS has enhanced their learning experience and that most of the areas for improvement identified after the joint workshop in Bratislava have been rectified. Those which need more work are:

- Tighter selection of students to ensure adequate English language ability
- Better linking of pre and post workshop tasks to workshop activities
- Social time early on to allow students to get to know each other better
- Increased free time for students to interact with each other and their local environment

The 2nd point contrasts with the view of the staff from the main partners, who felt they were able to establish good integration with their local programmes. For Associate Partners who joined the project already underway, integration was more difficult. The timing of key activities and the engagement of partners is clearly important, and this points to the need for a phased process of induction for new partners. Within the scope of a one year project this is extremely difficult, and for the future it would be useful if there were sources of funding designated to introduce and facilitate phased engagement of institutions with virtual campus environments. Such start-up funds would also facilitate wider use of the environments and expansion of the community of practice.

As previously, this year of OIKODOMOS has been a journey of exploration and development for everyone involved and has been very productive. The project has achieved all its major objectives, significantly expanding the community of teachers and learners, many who are committed to ongoing use of the virtual campus and to continued engagement in collaborative teaching activities, exchanges being supported where possible through Erasmus funding.

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7. APPENDICES

Appendix 1: OIKODOMOS Joint Workshop Student evaluation questionnaire

Workshop Theme: Housing and Proximity, Istanbul **Date: May 2011**

*This questionnaire is to help us develop the learning activities, processes and environments of OIKODOMOS. Your responses are important to help further guide developments of the environment, process and content used within Oikodomos and will be entered **anonymously** into a database and analysed. The results will be available through a report on the project web site, www.oikodomos.org.*

Please select the most appropriate option

Background information

1) Nationality: _____ **2) Gender:** Male Female

3) Age range: under 20 / 20-25 / 26-30 / 31-40 / over 40

4) Institution:

FASTU, Bratislava EMU, Eastern Mediterranean University ITU, Istanbul
Technical University

IUG, Grenoble URL La Salle, Barcelona Sint-Lucas, Ghent/Brussels

Other (please name)

5) Which Course are you on:

If you are an Erasmus student visiting one of these institutions please also give your home institution and it's country

5a) Level of study: Bachelor Masters **5b) Other?**.....

5c) Year of study 1st 2nd 3rd 4th 5th

6) Please underline all learning activities in which you participated and give the number of ECTS (if known)

Seminar	Specialised design studio
Design studio	Other

7) Did you participate in this Oikodomos Joint Workshop (identified in header)?

Yes No

8) Did you use the Workspace in the courses and seminars taking place at your university in conjunction with this Joint Workshop? Please select all that apply.

No Before During Not Applicable

9) Is this the first Oikodomos Joint Workshop you have attended?

Yes No

10) How do you rate your ability to use English?:

IELTS level if known.....

Other level if known (please specify).....

Speaking: poor basic intermediate fluent native

Reading: poor basic intermediate fluent native

Writing : poor basic intermediate fluent native

Educational process and Workspaces evaluation:

Evaluation of the Platforms and Process in the Design Studios and Seminars taking place at your School related to the this Joint Workshop

Please score each criteria according to the values given below. We would appreciate any comments or thoughts giving more information about the reasons for your score:

Pre workshop										
Evaluation Criteria					Scores					
1	Before going to the Joint Workshop I was clear about the purpose of the international cooperation in our (school) learning activities					A	B	C	D	E
	<i>Comments</i>									
2	The Learning Activities created by teachers in the Workspace were relevant and clear.					A	B	C	D	E
	<i>Comments</i>									
3	From the start of these activities I was given full descriptions of the learning activity, including learning objectives/outcomes					A	B	C	D	E
	<i>Comment</i>									
4	The learning activities in my school before going to the Joint Workshop were well integrated with the learning activities during the Joint Workshop					A	B	C	D	E
	<i>Comments</i>									
5	I used this Workshop Workspace regularly before the workshop to gain the information about the site.					A	B	C	D	E
	<i>Comment</i>									
6	Please estimate your overall degree of use of the tools below before and during the Workshop									
	Tool	Very low	Low	High	Very high					
	<i>Workspace</i>									
	<i>Case Study Repository</i>									
	<i>Other Internet sources</i>									
	<i>Google Maps, Earth, Groups...</i>									
	<i>AutoCAD</i>									
	<i>SketchUp</i>									
	<i>Photoshop</i>									
	<i>PowerPoint/Presenter</i>									
	<i>Communication tools (mail/chat, skype)</i>									
	<i>Other</i>									
7	Using these tools I was able to access enough information to prepare for the work during the Joint Workshop					A	B	C	D	E

	<i>Comments</i>					
8	Electronic/computer communication helped me to get-to know the participants from the other schools well enough to help collaboration before going to the Joint Workshop	A	B	C	D	E
	<i>Comments</i>					
9	The academic support at my university was sufficient for preparation of the learning activities to be carried out in the Joint Workshop	A	B	C	D	E
	<i>Comments</i>					
10	The processes to get technical and academic support were adequate	A	B	C	D	E
	<i>Comments</i>					
11	The response times to questions from learners by staff were adequate.	A	B	C	D	E
	<i>Comments</i>					
12	I discussed information on the Joint Workshop site with other students and teachers in advance of the workshop	A	B	C	D	E
	<i>Comments</i>					
13	I found students contributions to the discussions helpful	A	B	C	D	E
	<i>Comments</i>					
14	I found professors contribution to the discussions helpful	A	B	C	D	E
	<i>Comments</i>					
15	Working online collaboratively with students from other countries has been a good experience					
	<i>Comments</i>					
	Joint Workshop evaluation					
16	I was clear about the purpose/objective of the Joint Workshop when I arrived	A	B	C	D	E
	<i>Comments</i>					
17	The Introduction / briefing sessions made clear all aspects of the Joint Workshop	A	B	C	D	E
	<i>Comments</i>					
18	I was clear about the competences or learning outcomes to be gained from completing the workshop before arriving	A	B	C	D	E
	<i>Comments</i>					
19	I am clear about the way in which my work during the workshop will be assessed	A	B	C	D	E
	<i>Comments</i>					

20	The taught sessions were relevant and appropriate.	A	B	C	D	E
	<i>Comments</i>					
21	The taught sessions were clearly presented.	A	B	C	D	E
	<i>Comments</i>					
22	I thought the taught session were well integrated with the workshop theme	A	B	C	D	E
	<i>Comments</i>					
23	I thought the taught sessions fitted well with the work in groups	A	B	C	D	E
	<i>Comments</i>					
24	There was adequate access to computing resources	A	B	C	D	E
	<i>Comments</i>					
25	I had enough time to do the work	A	B	C	D	E
	<i>Comments</i>					
26	I had enough time not working / free time	A	B	C	D	E
	<i>Comments</i>					
27	I understand what work I have to do in my institution which follows on from this Joint Workshop	A	B	C	D	E
	<i>Comments</i>					
28	I was able to communicate effectively with the other members of my group	A	B	C	D	E
	<i>Comments</i>					
29	What was your most important or interesting learning?					
30	What did you like, was done well?					
31	What could be done differently?					
32	Any other comments?					
<p>We would like to organise some short, follow up meetings / discussions with individuals. If you are willing to participate please give your name and email address below.</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.</p> <p>Please return the completed questionnaire to your staff member/co-ordinator before leaving, or give it to Paul Riddy. If you have any questions please contact Paul Riddy, paul.riddy@virgin.net or get in touch with your local contact.</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Thank you for your time</p>						

Appendix 2. Cottbus Questionnaire and results

Oikodomos Case Study Repository Questionnaire Evaluation responses				
	Comments requested			
	Questions directly related to usability			
Q.No	Questionnaire No	1	2	3
	Date	Aug-11	Aug-11	Aug-11
	Location	Cottbus	Cottbus	Cottbus
1	Name			
2	Gender	M	M	F
3	Age	21	21	24
4	Did you have any difficulty logging in the Case Repository ?	N	Y	N
4.1	If yes, please describe		C	
5	Did you use the utility: "Most recent cases" located under the active Workspace name OIKODOMOS10_11?	Y	N	Y
6	Did you use the utility "Most graphic information cases" located under the active Workspace name OIKODOMOS10_11?	N	Y	N
7	Did you use the utility "Most tagged cases" located under the active Workspace name OIKODOMOS10_11?	N	Y	N
8	Did you take a look to the summary of the environment presented in SLIDESHOW	N		N
8.1	If yes, was it useful?			
9	Please indicate if you have any comment or suggestion to improve the logging in		C	
10	Did you use the Activity board to browse the most recent works? (on Log Screen)	Y	Y	Y
10.1	If yes, was it easy to use?	Y	Y	Y
11	Did you use the Activity board to access to one of the listed works directly?	Y	Y	Y
	If yes, was it easy to use?	Y	Y	Y
12	Please indicate if you have any comment or suggestion to improve the logging in			
13	Did you use the Users view? (Users Screen)	Y	Y	Y
13.1	If yes, did you use to have access to your works?	N	N	N
13.2	If yes, did you use to have access to the works of other students?	N		Y
14	Please indicate if you have any comment or suggestion to improve the User screen		C	
15	Did you use this screen to search for existing cases? (Case Studies Screen)	N	N	Y
15.1	If yes, did you use the pull-down menu (with the name Title) to select the category of the search (Title, Architect, Office, Country)?			
15.2	If yes, to question If yes to questions 15 and/or 15.1, did you use the filters TITLE, USER, ARCHITECT, YEAR, DATE to order the results of the search?			
16	Please indicate if you have any comment or suggestion to improve the Case studies screen			
17	Did you find any difficulty to introduce the IMAGES for your case study?	Y	N	N

18	Did you find any difficulty introducing the DESCRIPTIONS (Social, Economical and Technological factors; Individual, Communal and Urban spatial dimensions)?	Y	N	N
19	Was the meaning of the DESCRIPTIONS clear to you?	Y	Y	Y
20	Did you find any difficulty introducing any other element of the case study (Bibliography, Keywords, Tags)?	Y	N	Y
21	Please indicate if you have any comment or suggestion to improve the Case studies screen			
22	Did you find any difficulty to classify your case of study using the Keywords? (Keywords Screen)	N	Y	22-27 missing
23	Have you downloaded the PDF file which contains the complete classification?	N	N	
24	Did you use the classification to search for a case study?	Y	N	
25	Please indicate if you have any comment or suggestion to improve the Keyword screen		C	
26	Did you use the Tags screen to search for a case study? (Tags Screen)	N	N	
26.1	If yes, did you use search input box?			
27	If yes to previous question, did you use the filters NAME USER, DATE to order the results of the search?			
28	Please indicate if you have any comment or suggestion to improve the Tag screen			
29	Did you use the Bibliography screen to search for a bibliographic reference?		N	N
29.1	If yes, did you use the search input box?			
29.2	If yes to previous question, did you use the filters TITLE, AUTHOR, USER to order the results of the search?			
30	Please indicate if you have any comment or suggestion to improve the Tag screen			
31	What was <i>in general</i> the most difficult aspect you encountered in using the OIKODOMOS Case Repository?			
32	How do you evaluate your <i>overall</i> experience in using the OIKODOMOS Case Repository?			

Appendix 3: OIKODOMOS: Interview questions

Questions to guide the semi-structured interviews with **staff**:

October 2011

Joint workshop and L&T activities

1) How well aligned do you think your learning activities within your institution (pre and post) were with the joint workshop?... was there good integration of the L&T activities in your institution with those carried out collaboratively

2) With hindsight, is there anything you would like to improve/ do differently?

3) What was the quality of the student outputs?

The Future:

4) What do you think Oikodomos should do next?

Optional, if you have time:

Pedagogic model:

Below are listed the main elements of the pedagogic model. For each, please indicate:

- a) How easy or difficult this was to integrate with your normal L&T teaching approach
- b) What you think needs to be improved about this aspect of the pedagogic model and how.

5) designing Learning activities/tasks using an aligned learning and teaching methodology

- a.
- b.

6) blending learning activities / tasks within your institution with learning activities / tasks carried out collaboratively

- a.
- b.

7) blending local student and teacher activity with distant student and teacher activity

- a.
- b.

8) blending online activities with face-to-face joint workshops (pre and post joint workshop)

- a.
- b.

9) collaborative assessment and feedback to the students

- a.
- b.

Appendix 4: OIKODOMOS: Student Questionnaire, post workshop

This questionnaire was delivered online.

Please select the most appropriate option

Background information

1) **Nationality:** _____ 2) **Gender:** Male Female

3) **Age range:** under 20 / 20-25 / 26-30 / 31-40 / over 40

4) **Institution:**

FASTU, Bratislava Technical University EMU, Eastern Mediterranean University ITU, Istanbul

IUG, Grenoble URL La Salle, Barcelona Sint-Lucas, Ghent/Brussels

Other (please name)

5) **Which Course are you on:**

If you are an Erasmus student visiting one of these institutions please also give your home institution and it's country

5a) **Level of study:** Bachelor Masters 5b) **Other?**.....

5c) **Year of study** 1st 2nd 3rd 4th 5th

6) Please underline all learning activities in which you participated and give the number of ECTS (if known)

Seminar	Specialised design studio
Design studio	Elective
Other		

7) Did you participate in this Oikodemos Joint Workshop (identified in header)? Yes No

8) Did you use the Workspace in the courses and seminars taking place at your university in conjunction with this Joint Workshop? Please select all that apply.

No Before During Not Applicable

9) Is this the first Oikodemos Joint Workshop you have attended? Yes No

10) **What is your knowledge of English?:**

Speaking:	poor	basic	intermediate	fluent	native
Reading:	poor	basic	intermediate	fluent	native
Writing :	poor	basic	intermediate	fluent	native

11. Do you know your IELTS, TOEFL or other score? If so please give the name of the test/qualification and your score.

Data scaled :

1-4, Strongly agree, Agree, Disagree, Strongly disagree, + Don't know & Not Applicable N/A.

12	Before the workshop took place I used the OIKODOMOS Workspaces in conjunction with learning activities taking place at my university. - Please select
13	The relationship of the learning activities in your school to those during the Proximity workshop was clear to you from their beginning - Please select
14	The Learning Activities / Tasks created by teachers in the Proximity workspace were relevant, appropriate and clear. - Please select
15	From the start of these activities I was given full descriptions of the learning activity, including learning objectives/outcomes - Please select
16	Following the workshop, the Learning Activities / Tasks created by teachers in the Proximity Workspace were relevant, appropriate and clear. - Please select
17	In-school activities have been integrated and/or continue the activities begun during the workshop - Please select
18	I use the resources in the Workspace regularly to complete learning activities continuing after the workshop. - Please select
19	The learning process, including the use of the Workspace, has given me a multiplicity of viewpoints on the topic of Proximity. - Please select
20	Working online collaboratively with foreign partners has been a good experience. - Please select
21	Please estimate your overall use of the tools below (This is a repeat of a post-workshop question so we can look at any change in the use of tools) - <i>(Tools included the Oikodomos Workspaces and Case Repository)</i>
22	The Workspaces and tools were easy to use e.g. to search tasks, learning activities, resources files & groups; to add/view deliverables. - Please select
23	All necessary tools were included in the Workspaces e.g. to search tasks, learning activities, resources files & groups; to add/view deliverables. - Please select
24	All the learning resources in the Workspaces were easy to locate and access eg texts, references, site drawings. - Please select
25	I use the learning resources in the the Workspaces (eg information, deliverables, comments etc) to support the learning activities in my school eg modules, seminars, design studios. - Please select
26	The methods to obtain support for using the Workspaces worked well eg how to update your profile, how to do specific actions such as add task outputs - Please select
27	The response times to questions from learners by staff were adequate. - Please select
28	Using the Workspaces suits my way of working - Please select
29	The Workspaces provides a good environment in which to work collaboratively - Please select
30	What do you like, what is done well in the Workspaces?
31	What didn't you like, could be done differently?
32	Please include any other suggestions for improving the OIKODOMOS Workspaces.
33	We would like to organise some short, follow up meetings / discussions with individuals. If you are willing to participate please give your name and email address below.

Appendix 5: Analysis of the OIKODOMOS websites and blogs

See separate report